

Effect of weed control treatments on weed population, weed dry matter, and grain yield of rice.^a Coimbatore, India.

Treatment ^b	Timing ^c	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Weed population (no./m ²) at 40 DT				Total weed dry matter (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Cost of weed control (\$)
			Grass	Sedge	Dicot	Total			
EPTC + 2,4-D	PE	1.12+0.56	9.0 b	10.7 d	10.3 c	30.0 c	14.1 c	5.8 a	19.25
Molinate + 2,4-D	PE	1.80+0.56	3.7 a	2.0 a	3.8 a	9.5 a	10.1 ab	6.2 a	35.85
EPTC - propanil	EPE	1.44-1.44	20.2 c	13.5 e	11.3 c	45.0 d	19.9 d	5.5 a	27.64
Molinate - propanil	EPE	1.44-1.44	8.7 b	7.8 c	11.5 c	28.0 c	12.2 bc	5.9 a	40.00
Butachlor	PE	1.50	6.2 ab	7.5 c	6.3 b	20.0 b	13.8 c	5.8 a	20.73
Hand weeding twice		-	4.0 a	5.2 b	4.0 a	13.2 a	9.3 a	6.2 a	40.65
Unweeded check		-	104.5 d	31.5 f	38.0 d	174.0 e	73.5 e	3.1 b	-

^aMeans of four replications. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other by DMRT. ^b+ = tank mixture, - = proprietary mixture. ^cPE = preemergence, EPE = early postemergence.

in a field experiment at the university farm summer 1986. Treatments were EPTC + 2,4-D (ethyl ester), molinate + 2,4-D, and EPTC - propanil and molinate - propanil compared with butachlor, hand weeding twice (HWT), and an unweeded check. The herbicides were applied as preemergence (3 d after transplanting [DT]) or as early postemergence (12 DT).

Major weed flora in the experimental field were *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Echinochloa colona*, *Cyperus difformis*, *Eclipta prostrata*, *Ammannia baccifera*, and *Monochoria vaginalis*. Preemergence application of molinate + 2,4-D effectively controlled all three groups of weeds (see table).

At 40 DT, grass weed control by

molinate + 2,4-D was comparable with that by butachlor; control of sedge and broadleaf weeds was superior to all other herbicides. Molinate - propanil and EPTC + 2,4-D also were promising. HWT was comparable with molinate + 2,4-D. Costs of weed control were highest for hand weeding twice and molinate - propanil. □

Effect of time and method of application of herbicides on yield and yield components of rainfed lowland rice

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We studied the effect of time and method of herbicide application on yield and yield components of rainfed lowland rice during wet season 1987. Four herbicides were applied with sand or water at different rates and times. Butachlor, thiobencarb, and pendimethalin were applied at 1.5 kg ai/ha, 2,4-D at 0.9 kg ai/ha, in 1,000 liter water/ha or in 60 kg sand/ha.

BPT2740 was drill seeded on unpuddled soil 17 Aug 1987. Fertilizer was 100 kg N as urea, 17 kg P as single superphosphate, and 50 kg K as muriate of potash/ha. The crop was grown under rainfed condition to 40 d after seeding (DAS), then irrigated. Weed dry weight was measured 60 DAS.

Butachlor applied 1 DAS was equivalent to hand weeding (see table). Pendimethalin at 1 DAS or 2,4-D at 7

Effect of time and method of application of herbicides on weed growth and yield of rainfed lowland rice.

Treatment ^a	Weed dry weight log transformed values ^b	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Butachlor 1 DAS	12.6 (160)	273	111	3.3
Butachlor 7 DAS	38.2 (1460)	200	86	2.5
Butachlor 7 DAS with sand	43.9 (1930)	205	51	1.7
Thiobencarb 1 DAS	31.4 (990)	189	62	1.9
Thiobencarb 7 DAS	29.8 (890)	241	101	2.8
Thiobencarb 7 DAS with sand	30.6 (933)	235	100	2.7
2,4-D EE 1 DAS	40.8 (1660)	187	102	2.6
2,4-D EE 7 DAS	22.7 (513)	262	105	3.1
Pendimethalin 1 DAS	19.2 (367)	265	106	3.2
Hand weeding 20 and 40 DAS	2.4 (5)	277	112	3.5
Unweeded control	52.2 (2833)	5	23	0.1
LSD (0.05)	(16.5)	72	13	2.9

^aDAS = days after sowing. ^bValues in parentheses are weed wt in kg/ha.

DAS was similar to butachlor applied 1 DAS. □